

Topic: CIRC BIO-01-01 Circular Cities and Regions Initiative's project development assistance (CCRI-PDA)

D5.5 - Report on the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities and results – first period

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D5.5 - Report on the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities and results – first period

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1. Introduction

1.1. Objective and Purpose

1.1.1. What is DECISO?

Investment is the seed for growing a circular economy. The project ‘DEvelopers of Circular SOLUTIONS’ (DECISO) aims to support European cities and regions to develop financing schemes for circular economy (CE) initiatives. DECISO uses an ecosystem approach: it will explore how circular economy business plans can be tailored to different geographical, economic, natural, and social environments. Based on this, DECISO will establish guidelines for financing schemes which other European cities and regions can use for their circular economy initiatives. DECISO partners have set up four pilot projects to test the development of such schemes, before facilitating their replication:

- City Hamburg: the City of Hamburg (FHH) will develop and implement financial schemes for circular economy at the city or sectoral level, by engaging, among others, finance institutions and partners. The goal is to mobilise investments from regional agencies, SMEs and industries that will complement the budget allocated to the circular economy through the Hamburg Climate Plan.
- Alentejo: the Commission for Coordination and Regional Development of Alentejo (CCDRA) will support local authorities and their associations in the definition and development of financial schemes for circular systemic solutions in the agri-food sector.
- Northwestern Germany: the Oldenburgisch-Ostfriesischer Wasserverband (OOWV), one of the largest water service providers in Germany, aims at exploring the potential of rainwater use in rural areas and to develop circular economy concepts such as water reuse.
- Western Macedonia: the Municipal District Heating Company of the Wider Region of Amyntaio (MDHA) wants to implement a circular economy project that exploits biomass and residues/wastes and hereby prevents energy poverty.

1.1.2. Actors of DECISO

The DECISO project is run by a consortium of 10 partners from 5 countries, representing 2 research organisations, 2 public authorities, 2 public suppliers, 3 private companies and 1 non-profit association.

In addition, in each pilot, stakeholders along the value chain have a crucial role. They will be engaged throughout the project and their input will allow the development of robust business plans. This, in return, shall foster the interest of investors and support from the local community.

Figure 1: DECISO Consortium

1.1.3. Activities and impacts

Figure 2: Project phases and timeline of project implementation

DECISO is implemented in different phases. A first set of activities (WP1) serves to analyse the state of the art of the markets in the pilot areas. Furthermore, knowledge will be gathered and shared within the Consortium on existing financing schemes and good practices. Starting in parallel, another set of activities is mapping and engaging important stakeholders in the pilot areas. The goal is to establish working groups for each of the circular economy programs. Ultimately, these activities aim at fostering support among different stakeholders and ensuring political commitment to the programs. Based on the analysis carried out, the DECISO partners will develop technical solutions (WP3 and WP4), namely financing schemes and concrete

business plans. The goal is also to develop operational services for different stakeholder groups involved in investment in CE projects. A last set of activities (WP5) aims at sharing information on DECISO with a larger set of stakeholders, including in other EU regions. Communication will also be two-sided, meaning engaging in a dialogue with different stakeholder groups. Last, the learnings and technical solutions developed will be exploited to develop guidelines that should incite other regions to replicate the adopted schemes and to get the stone rolling in the multiplication of CE programs.

1.2. Report on communication, dissemination and exploitation activities

This report provides an account of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities undertaken by the DECISO partners in the first period of the project (November 2022 until April 2024). The goal of this report is two-fold: summarising these activities and evaluating their effectiveness. On the one hand, it informs on the impact of the activities on the project objectives and the status of communication and dissemination KPIs. On the other one, especially in the case of the exploitation strategy, it enables the DECISO partners to look forward and anticipate the second period of the project, adapting when relevant the activities planned initially to better reach the objectives set. Since the first tangible results to disseminate and exploit started to be produced after the first year of the project and progress are currently ongoing, the main content of the report is an overview of the activities related to communication.

The report is divided into four parts. The first one explains the impact of communication, dissemination, and exploitation on the overall goal of the project to ensure that the messages, targeted stakeholders, tools and channels created are appropriately used. In the second part, the different communication and dissemination activities undertaken are described channel by channel, assessing their performance. A third part monitors where the project stands regarding the KPIs, having in mind to explore actions to take to not just meet but exceed KPIs. A fourth and final part focuses on the exploitation strategy, looking ahead to the upcoming months of the project and re-assessing the exploitation strategy to ensure a long-lasting legacy of DECISO.

2. Communicating, disseminating, and exploiting DECISO

2.1. Communication and dissemination

Communication and dissemination are a key element of the DECISO project, to build a strong ecosystem, involving all stakeholders. The ultimate objective is to create communities that support circular economy initiatives and contribute to their development. Indeed, having engaged local communities guarantees the social acceptance of solutions developed at pilot level and reinforces strong political commitment at this level. In this sense, communication is strongly linked to stakeholder engagement (WP 2, Task 1). Communication activities aim at informing and raising awareness about the DECISO project and the larger topic of the circular economy. Dissemination activities are and will be used to present and discuss the technical results of the project in more detail.

Communication and Dissemination activities accompany the project from the beginning until the end, under the lead of ACR+ and with the active support and involvement of all partners. The document D5.1 Communication Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy describes in detail these activities and their goal. It is completed by a communication kit (templates, messaging, visual identity).

Three tools have been developed to prepare the communication and dissemination activities (available in the D5.1.): the stakeholder typology and matrix (enabling to better understand and target stakeholders) and

the communication matrix (summarising key messages, the objectives and the communication channels for each target group).

2.2. *Exploitation*

From the early stages of the project, the use of its results in public policymaking has been carefully taken into consideration and planned. The overarching exploitation goal is to outline the DECISO project's exploitable results, and the key partners involved. As clearly indicated in its title, a section of the D5.1 Communication Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy is dedicated to exploitation. This initial version plans a five-steps strategy to comply with the mission of “creating an impact beyond the project implementation and ensuring the broadest use of its results while maximising the partners’ payoff”. Briefly, these are:

1. Understand the partners’ requests and elicit the stakeholders’ needs.
2. Aggregate information and map the territorial needs.
3. Analysis of DECISO’s exploitable results, the grounding IPRs, and replicability or scalability to other contexts.
4. Outline exploitation paths and recommendations-guidelines.
5. Define the boundaries and opportunities for DECISO’s replication and feasibility, also considering the stakeholders’ feedback.

The assumption made from the beginning relies on the concept that the roles and responsibilities of the actors involved in circular economy often vary between territories and different cultural, political, geographical, historical, and economic contexts. In fact, there is no one common approach or governance model for the CE deployment when it involves a wide range of actors – from the highest levels of government to civil society groups, from institutions to developers, or from entrepreneurs to marginalized social groups and young people, as well as future generations.

2.3 *Impact on the project*

During the first period of DECISO, a great deal of efforts has indeed been put on creating awareness of DECISO and on setting a strong basis for effective dissemination and exploitation with relevant tools and processes. Giving its identity to the project is an important component to the recruitment of stakeholders. It can be said that all partners have adopted the visual identify of the project and are actively using the tools at their disposal (made available on the shared space of the project managed by CNR) to communicate on the project, reinforcing the common approach at the core of the project and contributing to its identification as a strong, unique entity by the different stakeholders.

Figure 3: Example of use of the roll-up and PPT template during an event organised by the University of Western Macedonia in December 2023

Being equipped with a strong identity of the project and with tools they are familiar with, it will be easier for partners to effectively implement the activities of the pilots and promote the first results of the project. In this sense, the type and quantity of communication activities will take another turn after this first reporting period. As the programmes and strategies will be launched by the pilots, there will be an increase in the data and content produced under the work package 5.

3. Overview of tools and activities

3.1. Website

The DECISO website is the project’s main communication tool and window on all activities. It is available at the following address: <https://www.decisoproject.eu>. It is technically hosted and managed by CNR supported by ACR+ and with inputs from all partners.

The website is the general interface with stakeholders and reaches out to the largest range of stakeholders. It provides general information about the DECISO project, its activities and expected impacts, an overview of each of the pilot CE initiatives as well as direct access to some of the DECISO resources.

The DECISO website hosts the DECISO Digital Ecosystem tool (DECISO-DE) which has been configured by CNR as the interactive hub of all the other activities organised within the project and the other channels and as the communication system of the DECISO community. It is accessible from DECISO Digital Ecosystem menu on the website. CNR configured and manages DECISO-Digital Ecosystem on its secure servers.

Since its launch in June 2023, the website comprises 16 pages, 18 news and events articles. It attracted 1 195 users, totalising 7 524 views. Overall, the number of users per month has been steadily increasing, with peaks in September and December 2023. Regarding page views, the numbers are more unequal with no clear trend visible but clear peaks in June, September, December 2023 and February 2024. These peaks are

linked with key events such as right after the workshop with the HOOP project (in May), announcing the project’s GA, and the newsletter publication.

Figure 4: Total number of active users on the DECISO website between June 2023 and April 2024

Figure 5: Total number of visits to the website between June 2023 and April 2024

Visitors to the website come mainly from Italy, followed by Germany and Ireland. They are mainly using a desktop computer (83%). The most visited page is the homepage (1 671 views), the eco-system (1 276 views), the pilots page (986), and the page introducing the project (345). In average, users spend 1m29s on the website, which is compatible with the average length of news and events published on the website.

Figure 6: Origin of users per country

Traffic acquisition: Session primary channel group (Default channel group)

Session primary...channel group	↓ Users	Sessions	Engaged sessions	Average engagement time
	1,195 100% of total	2,174 100% of total	1,173 100% of total	1n A
1 Direct	923	1,518	752	1n
2 Organic Search	218	501	356	1n
3 Unassigned	42	49	0	
4 Organic Social	28	32	15	
5 Referral	22	71	50	2n
6 Organic Video	1	1	1	1n

Figure 7: Overview of acquisition of the DECISO website

3.2. Social media

DECISO is present with an account on the following social media channels: X (former Twitter), LinkedIn and Facebook. Partners also ensure the visibility of the project using their own accounts (personal or from the organisation).

The hashtag #DECISO_EU is used across all social media posts, including local social media channels. Posts generally include a reference and link to the DECISO website to drive traffic there.

3.2.1. X (former Twitter)

The X page of the project [@DECISOproject](#) counts with 30 followers. 21 posts have been published, totalising 5570 impressions and 760 engagements including 120 retweets, 280 likes, 90 profile clicks, and 80 link clicks.

Once again, the most popular post is related to the [event organised with HOOP](#).

Figure 8: Most popular post on X

3.2.2. LinkedIn

The [LinkedIn page of the project](#) counts 97 followers, 193 unique visitors and its page has been visited 430 times. Over 25 posts have been published, totalising 5 297 impressions, 79 reposts, 248 clicks and 277 likes. The number of monthly impressions is generally on the rise, indicating a stronger visibility of the project on the social media.

The most reposted posts are about the [event with HOOP on 10 May 2023](#) (11 reposts) and the [webinar on 30 April on financial challenges](#) (7 reposts).

Figure 9: Evolution of the number of followers of the DECISO LinkedIn page

Metrics

Figure 10: Number of impressions of the LinkedIn posts

Visitor metrics

Figure 11: Number of views of the DECISO page on LinkedIn

Visitor metrics

Figure 12: Number of unique visitors of the DECISO page on LinkedIn

DECISO project
92 follows
1w • Edited •

What are the #financial challenges that hinder the #circulareconomy? Which strategy could overcome them?

Explore the answers that the DECISO pilots can bring to these questions during a webinar organised by InvestCEC project in cooperation with DECISO.

30 April 2024
11:00 - 12:30 CET
Online

Agenda and registration: <https://lnkd.in/d/MVnpXJA>

Just like DECISO, InvestCEC belongs to the projects implemented under the umbrella of the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI). It will develop a replicable model for the initiation of circular economy projects in cities and regions, that will improve collaboration between entrepreneurs, investors and policy makers. More: <https://investcec.eu>

Oldenburgisch-Ostfriesischer Wasserverband (OÖWV) KOYS srl University of Western Macedonia IRADIARE Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche ACR+ | Association of Cities and Regions for sustainable Resource management ÖV Group SpA (Officinae Verdi Group SpA)

Join Part Two of the InvestCEC Webinar Series: Breaking Down Financial Barriers
In Collaboration with InvestCEC and DECISO
Date: Tuesday, 30 April - Time: 11:00 - 12:30 CET on Teams

Agenda Highlights

- Overcoming Financial Barriers in the Circular Economy, Jorge Galva Press, CARTIF
- Hamburg: Strategic Framework for Financial Schemes Sabine Herrmann, City of Hamburg
- North-West Germany: Optimize rainwater use, Daniel Dendek, ÖÖWV
- West Macedonia: Decarbonization and post-Signia transition Kostas Karamarkos, DETEPA
- Asteriga: Circular agri-food business models, Rosa Dnoffe, CCIRA

Powered by The European Union InvestCEC DECISO

Sabine Herrmann and 15 others 7 reports

Reactions: Interesting! I like... Love it... Sharing this... Love this... I think

Like Comment Repost

Comment as DECISO project...

Figure 13: Most popular post on LinkedIn

3.2.3. Facebook

The [Facebook page of the project](#) counts 21 followers and 18 likes, it has been visited 283 times with clear peaks around the project's main events and displays a reach of 801.

26 posts have been posted on the Facebook page, totalising 1714 impressions. The most popular post is about the [release of the newsletter](#).

Figure 14: Beginning of the DECISO page on Facebook

Figure 15: Overview of the visits of the Facebook page between May 2023 and April 2024

Figure 16: Overview of the Facebook page reach between May 2023 and April 2024

Figure 17: Most popular post on Facebook

3.2.4. DECISO partners channels and external

Partners have also been actively promoting DECISO on their own social media channels, publishing at least 20 posts for an estimated 6226 impressions (cf. Annexe – table 11 Reach of social media posts).

Posts by external stakeholders are also mentioning DECISO, such as EGEN or HOOP project in May 2023.

Figure 18: Post by an external stakeholder mentioning DECISO

3.3. Newsletter

DECISONews, as indicated by its name, is the newsletter of the project. It aims at providing information about the project's activities, its results, but also the developments in the field of circular economy. The first issue has been published in December 2023.

To maximise the dissemination and impact of the newsletter, it has been decided to prepare two versions. A long version is available as a [PDF, ready to be downloaded from the website](#). It has been prepared in a way that it can be read offline, guaranteeing that it stays informative and relevant even without visiting the links included. In this way, if needed, the newsletter can be printed and disseminated as a stand-alone document or complementing the leaflet.

In addition, to make it more online user-friendly and to keep engaging stakeholders in the mailing list, [an email/online version of the newsletter](#) has been prepared and sent on 29 January 2024 to 40 recipients from ACR+ and each partner sent it to their network. It has been opened by 25.71% of the recipients and the click rate is of 5%.

The newsletter has been promoted on all social networks. The second issue will be produced by June 2024.

3.4. Contact and mailing list

A contact list has been created, compiling data from stakeholders interested in being updated about DECISO or willing to take a more active role in the project. It is hosted on the website EU Survey and managed by CNR and ACR+. Personal data are collected and managed according to the procedures described in "D6.4. Data collection and processing" and "D6.5 Data Management Plan – initial". The type of stakeholders to be included in the contact list are identified following the strategy described in "D2.1 Stakeholders' engagement

strategy”. A rapid increase of KPIs outreach, especially concerning the number of contacts included in the project stakeholders list, is expected starting from M20, when partners will focus on implementing local action plans. It is possible to join the contact list by filing an online form: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/ca55dfe0-43ac-f114-7efb-48bfaad5106f>. Participants of the project’s conference and local workshops were also given the opportunity to subscribe to the mailing list through a paper version of the signature lists. In April 2024, the contact lists included 155 stakeholders.

Building on this contact list, a mailing list has been created to easily email (unless it has been stated that they don’t want to receive any communication). In April 2024, the mailing list contains 145 contacts (excluding partners). The mailing software Brevo is used to send newsletters and other communications like invitations to events, announcements of publications and reports.

In addition to the first issue of the newsletter, an [email invitation](#) to a webinar organised on 30 April with InvestCEC project has been sent on 26 April 2024 to 144 contacts.

3.5. Promotional material

An overview of the promotional material produced is offered below, providing an overview of the copies disseminated and their reach, when relevant.

3.5.1. Leaflets

Two leaflets have been created for distribution at conferences, meetings, and other events. The first one offers a general presentation of DECISO whereas the second focuses on pilot (one leaflet per pilot). All leaflets have been prepared in English and translated by pilots when necessary. They are available on the [website](#).

Figure 19: The DECISO leaflet unfolded

The leaflet has been printed by partners and distributed at the following events:

- University of Western Macedonia mutual learning and dissemination workshops (50 copies)
- Pop-up circular hub (13/04/2024 – Hamburg)
- Mutual Learning Workshop, Hamburg (06/09/2023) (17 copies)

- Mutual Learning Workshop, Alentejo (28/06/2023) (20 copies)
- Mutual Learning Workshop, Macedonia (30/11/2023) (12 copies)

3.5.2. Factsheets

A factsheet on the state of the art of the market for circular economy in each pilot territory has been prepared (four in total) and made available on the [website](#). When relevant, pilots translated them to make it easier to disseminate at local level and to increase their reach.

3.6. Other online activities

Partners engaged in other online activities promoting DECISO namely:

- Webpage about DECISO on partners’ website: [Hamburg](#), [ACR+](#), [West Macedonia](#), [Irradiare](#)
- Articles in partners’ newsletters: ACR+ ([08/04/2024](#); [22/04/2024](#); [13/11/2023](#); [23/10/2023](#); [15/05/2023](#); [12/04/2023](#))

Figure 20: Page about DECISO on the Hamburg website

Figure 21: News article about DECISO in the ACR+ newsletter

In addition, DECISO has been mentioned on the following channels:

- [InvestCEC website news article](#) (27/03/2024)
- [InvestCEC newsletter #3](#) (28/03/2024)
- [HOOP event page](#) (10/05/2023)
- [Presentation of the CCRI projects](#) at the 5th OECD Roundtable on the Circular Economy in Cities and Regions and CoR ENVE Seminar (5-6 June 2023 – Tallin and online)
- [Database of the activities of the coordination group of the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform](#) (10/05/2023)

3.7. Media relations

Two press releases have been sent by the University of Western Macedonia in relation to the workshop conducted on 07/12/2023:

- <https://www.uowm.gr/epikairota/deltia-typoy/oloklirose-tis-ergasies-tis-i-ekdilosi-paroyiasis-toy-ergoy-deciso-sto-panepistimio-dytikis-makedonias/>
- <https://ucri.uowm.gr/anaskopisi-tis-ekdilosis-parousiasis-tou-ergou-deciso-sto-panepistimio-dytikis-makedonias/>

3.8. Events

3.8.1. DECISO Workshops and conferences

The events listed in the table below took place during the first period, organised by DECISO partners. If these events are often activities planned under other work packages (e.g. WP1, WP3), there are highly relevant to WP5 as they contribute to the visibility of the project (towards all invited participants) and to raising

stakeholders’ awareness about the existence of DECISO. Also, during all these events, DECISO-branded materials are used, which fosters the strong identity of the project.

Table 1: Reach of the DECISO events

Event name	Date	Reach
National participatory workshop Hamburg	26/06/2023	32
National participatory workshop Alentejo		35
National participatory workshop Western Macedonia	03/07/2023	15
National participatory workshop Northwest Germany	26/04/2023	
Mutual Learning workshop Hamburg	06/09/2023	50
Mutual Learning workshop Alentejo	28/06/2023	20
Mutual Learning workshop Western Macedonia	30/11/2023	12
Mutual Learning workshop Northwest Germany	23/08/2023	40
Financing local circular economy initiatives - HOOP/DECISO workshop	10/05/2023	2887
TOTAL REACH		3091

Figure 22: Photos from the HOOP/DECISO workshop

3.8.2. External events

DECISO has been promoted at various external events, either by a presentation part of the official programme or by engaging in networking activities with fellow participants.

- **Participation in the various CCRI working groups throughout 2023-2024** (with first results to be share in the upcoming reporting period)

- Circular Economy Hotspot (29/05 – 01/06/2023) and ACR+ General Assembly 2023:** ACR+ had a stand at the Circular Economy Hotspot 2023 where it displayed and made available the DECISO leaflet. In addition, the DECISO project has been mentioned to ACR+ members and guests during its general assembly 2023.

Figure 23: ACR+ stand at the Circular Economy Hotspot 2024

- Circular Cities and Regions Initiative first conference (08/11/2023):** DECISO was part of the poster exhibition of the event as well as KOYS, CCDR, and CNR engaged in networking activities with other participants.

Figure 24: DECISO partners at the CCRI first conference in front of the DECISO poster

- Ecomondo 2023 (7-10/11/2023):** CNR and ACR+ were present at Ecomondo and exchanged with relevant projects (like Hubs4Circularity) about the green transition and circular economy. In addition, leaflets were available at the European Research Executive Agency stand.

Figure 25: Pictures from Ecomondo

- **Local events:** at local level, the four pilots joined events and meetings to present DECISO.

3.8.3. Reach

Table 2: Reach of external events where DECISO was promoted

Event name	Location	Date	Reach
2 nd Forum CE Hamburg “Circular Cities”	Hamburg	12/04/2023	50
Kick-off meeting of the KARMA project	Hamburg	24/05/2023	50
Circular Economy Hotspot	Dublin	29/05 – 01/06/2023	100
ACR+ General Assembly	Dublin	31/05 – 01/06/2023	55
Circular Cities and Regions Conference	Brussels	08/11/2023	100
ECOMONDO 2023	Rimini	09-10/11/2023	30
Financing and funding of circular business models and innovation	Hamburg	24/11/2023	1300
Cost efficiency in circular construction	Hamburg	28/11/2023	25
Pop-up Circular Hub	Hamburg	20/11 – 07/12/2023	1 200
Open Day in JUPITER	Hamburg	13/04/2024	100 000
WCEF2024 Side-Event: Hamburg and Opening of Pop-Up Circular Hub	Hamburg	30/04/2024	Data will be available for next reporting period

Breaking Down Financial Barriers – InvestCEC webinar	Online	30/04/2024	Data will be available for next reporting period
TOTAL REACH			102 910

4. Towards reaching the KPIs

4.1. KPIs

The table below provides an overview of where DECISO stands regarding the indicators set at the beginning of the project in order to demonstrate successful communication and dissemination.

Table 3: Key Performance Indicators for Communication and Dissemination activities

Tool	Target audience	KPI	Achievement Y1	By when?
Scientific publications (open access) and conference presentations	Researchers, academics, policymakers, enterprises, financial actors and citizens	Min. 6 peer-reviewed publications, reaching a minimum of 500 people of the target audience	-	End of project
Annual conferences in yr. 2 and 3	Researchers and academics	Min. 200 participants in total	-	Yr. 2 and 3
Open Data, Open Access and Open Source results	Researchers, academics, policymakers, enterprises, financial actors and citizens	Min. 100 downloads in the last 12 months of the project	-	End of project
DECISO website and social media	Researchers, academics, policymakers, enterprises, financial actors and citizens	Min. 12 000 web visits/year, min. 42 000 cross-linking with social media accounts, referencing and SEO	7 524 visits for year 1 18 572 cross-linking on social media accounts (cf. annex 1)	End of project
Internal Communication Training	Consortium partners	2 trainings for min. 20 persons to increase outreach success by partners by 50-100% (take-up of press releases and impressions of social	Introduction session to communication during the project's kick-off meeting	End of project

		media posts by partners)		
Promotional Content (printed and online): 1 leaflet, 4 Brochures in the pilot areas (one per pilot), 5+ postcards, 6 infographics, 4 fact-sheets (one per pilot), 5 roll-ups (1 for the project and 4, one per pilot area) and posters.	Researchers, academics, policymakers, enterprises, financial actors and citizens	Min. 10 000 stakeholders reached through promotional actions	107 671 stakeholders reached (cf. annex 1)	Various
Journalistic content	Media outlets, associations, citizens	Min. 8 interviews (two per pilot area), min. 8 press releases (2 per pilot area), 5 newsletters	1 newsletter sent to 40 contacts and partners' mailing lists 2 press releases	Interviews and press releases (see Table 5) Newsletters: 1 in yr 1, 2 in yr 2, 2 in yr 3

4.2. First lessons learnt

The monitoring of online activities shows the project's visibility across the different channels slowing taking off. A first KPI, linked to the number of stakeholders reached, has been already reached, nonetheless this is mainly due to a very good promotion opportunity taken by Hamburg. Thus, partners are encouraged to continue working on the promotional actions, especially by ensuring that DECISO is represented at the main events in the field as it has been the case since its start.

To guarantee that the other KPIs are reached, more efforts will have to be done by the partners on their own channels to strengthen the local and regional reach of the project. DECISO is producing the most relevant outcomes with WP3 and WP4 starting from April 2024. This means that the communication and dissemination activities must be intensified in the second period of activities of the project. To increase DECISO's reach at international level (but not only), a list of "replication" channels will be established with the goal of using their audience and visibility. In addition, the reporting will be made easier to encourage partners to regularly indicate the reach of their posts and various publications.

As it is visible that events coincide with an increase in the visits to the website and thus higher possibilities for the target audience to get familiar with the project and its outcomes, mainly in the second period, communicating and disseminating the results of WP3 and WP4. Thus, a specific attention will be given to promoting events on the website (and the DECISO-DE), and making connections between activities displayed on the website, between pages related to these activities. Attendance of external events will be more promoted on social media as it often results in an increase in views.

By working on raising the profile of the DECISO-DE and reinforcing its use by other projects and related-initiatives for dissemination purposes, partners will be bringing more visitors to the DECISO website. Efforts will be made to keep visitors engaged and staying on the website by including links to the DECISO website in the articles (news, events) on the DECISO-DE, adding clear link to other content located on the website, and preparing engaging pages. This will in turn contribute to reach the KPI linked to the web visits,

Regarding social networks, trends (for example linked to popular events in the field such as Ecomondo or the Green Week) will be used to increase DECISO’s profile and channel views of the website. We will continue to make reference to the website as much as possible to create traffic there.

The Social Media Guide, made available to partners on the shared cloud, has been modified to include tools specifically aiming at increasing the visibility of DECISO profiles on various social media and guaranteeing that the related KPI is reached. Partners are invited not only to share DECISO content on their channels but also to suggest content to be shared on DECISO channels, with at least a contribution per partner per month (with ACR+ in charge of publishing them). Content shared will not be limited to news about DECISO and can also cover relevant news and updates (for example from sister-projects) so DECISO channels become a place where to go for information. Interactions with followers and other accounts will also be encouraged.

Finally, it is expected to see an increase of communication activities since it will soon be possible to promote the first deliverables, which will make it easier to trigger interest and drive engagement. An intensification of the collaboration with CCRI, and with other projects and initiatives related to DECISO (as specified in the deliverable D5.8) will facilitate the communication process, and the dissemination and communication on digital media is encouraged. For example, trying to have articles on DECISO in other CCRI projects. Public deliverables, once approved, will be shared on the DECISO-DE and in Zenodo. In the second period, articles in scientific journals will be produced.

5. Progress of exploitation activities

5.1. DECISO exploitation survey on KERs and needs mapping

Starting from the preliminary list of exploitable results (KER), and horizontal activities (HR) planned to contribute to project’s outcomes’ achievement as discussed in the GA (table 5), and leveraging the stakeholders’ workshops campaign, it has been possible to enhance the DECISO’s vision and refine a list of possible additional KERs.

Table 4: Initial list of Key Exploitable Results and Horizontal Activities for DECISO

Initial list of Key Exploitable Results and Horizontal Activities
KER 1: CEE Strategy for Stakeholders’ engagement. Document addressed to stakeholders: Local policymakers, regional/city development agencies, city administrations, Urban designers, design thinkers, NGOs, Researchers
KER 2: CEE co-design approach for developing circular economy projects. Document addressed to stakeholders: City development agencies, city administrations, Urban designers, design thinkers, NGOs, Researchers.
KER 3: Portfolio of sustainable practices, processes, business models, financing schemes. Models and schemes for stakeholders: local authorities, researchers, producers, retailers, consumers, logistics.

HR1 Trained circular economy actors in local administration. Events for stakeholders: Researchers, City administration, Policymakers

HR2 Scientific, industrial and societal awareness. Activities for stakeholders: Scientific community, Wide public.

During the mapping process, a substantial list of potential KERs has been scouted in the pilots' activities. In detail, and by categories, these are:

- **Documents and Reports [D&R]:** documents extracting and outlining guidelines on how to replicate the DECISO Circular Economy Ecosystem approach in other urban and regional contexts. These are relevant for starting mobilising and engaging stakeholders in CEE' dynamics.
 1. Guidelines for CEE Strategy.
 2. Policy recommendations for implementing a supporting environment for CE ideas from startups, SMEs, civil society.
 3. Business plan related to circular economy in the Agri-food sector (proposal).
 4. Report with the Agri-food circular economy funding schemes.
 5. Document regarding a common SWOT analysis of the CE in the pilots (identify the similarities inside the pilots regarding the circularity).

- **Procedures and Practices [P&P]:** Documents listing potential solutions suitable for CEE strategies' implementation in territories. These constitute a set of blueprints that need a preliminary feasibility and adaptation analysis for medium-term exploitable CEE procedures.
 1. CEE co-design approach for developing circular economy projects.
 2. Portfolio of sustainable practices, processes, business models with high replicability potential, financing schemes, PDA establishment and involvement
 3. CEE Strategy for Stakeholders' engagement.
 4. Analysis and development of documents focusing on the overall process of a project proposal presentation for a European funding programme (For example, a step-by-step guide)
 5. Definition of structured approach to the project development of circular economy initiatives in the field of rainwater harvesting.
 6. Explore and develop innovative rainwater use solutions that can effectively address water scarcity and promote sustainability.

- **Actions and Initiatives [A&I]:** Constitute real on-field operative activities targeting at supporting CEE' initiatives. Their goal – in the DECISO ecosystem – is to provide stakeholders with usable tools and solutions for quasi-ready CEE initiatives to be implemented in the very short term.
 1. Funds supporting the projects' implementation.
 2. Alentejo region Circular economy in the Agri-food sector projects portfolio.

3. PDA documents.
 4. solutions including advanced rainwater harvesting techniques, intelligent surface water management, and targeted infiltration strategies.
 5. suitable financing schemes, pursuing grant-funded projects, and leveraging partnerships to overcome financial barriers and facilitate project implementation.
- **Networking [NET]:** Operative activities and actions focusing on stakeholders’ mapping and active engagement in CEE’ initiatives. These are horizontal exploitable actions supporting stakeholders in their journey through the CEE planning and implementation.
 1. Establishment of a well-functioning CE network in Hamburg with a contact point /CE hub which can be reached for any questions regarding CE.
 2. List of circular economy actors in the Agri-food sector in Alentejo (identify entities supporting the development of financial schemes).
 3. collaborative partnerships to foster knowledge exchange, share best practices, and promote collective action towards sustainable water management.
 4. sharing expertise, providing guidance to other regions, and contributing to the broader conversation on sustainable water management practices.

The following table maps each KERs with stakeholders’¹ interests and needs. Four levels of relevance are described:

Table 5: Maps of KERs with stakeholders’ interest

Table legend

Not interested	Potentially interested	Mostly addressing needs	Highly addressing needs
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Category	KER	LRA	PU	F	E	P	R	C
Documents and Reports	1	High	mostly	high		mostly		mostly
	2	high		mostly	high	high		mostly
	3	high	Mostly	high	Potential	mostly		
	4	high	Mostly	high			Mostly	
	5	Potential	Potential	High	Potential	high	high	

¹ other regions/municipalities (LRA); Public utility company (PU); Financial actors (F); Enterprise / consulting (E); Policymakers (P); Research / Academia (R); Citizens / NGO (C)

Procedures and Practices	1	High	High	Potential	Mostly	Potential	Potential	Potential
	2	High	High	High	Potential			Potential
	3	High	High	Potential		Mostly		Potential
	4	High	Potential	Mostly	Mostly		Mostly	
	5	High	Potential	Potential	Mostly	Potential	Mostly	Potential
	6	Mostly	High			Mostly	High	Mostly
Actions and Initiatives	1	High	High	High		High		High
	2	Mostly		Potential		Mostly	Mostly	Potential
	3	High	High	High	Potential	High		
	4	high		Mostly	Potential		Mostly	Mostly
	5	high						
Networking	1	Potential	Mostly	Mostly	high	high	Potential	high
	2	Potential	Mostly	Mostly	high	High	Potential	high
	3	Mostly	Potential		Mostly		Potential	Potential
	4	high	high			high		Mostly

Additional KERs will also be checked within the project deliverables (table 6)

Table 6: DECISO deliverables feeding into KERs

Name of the result	Target group	Month of delivery
D.1.1 Market state of the art of circular economy in the pilot areas	Internal & external	12
D.1.2 Guide to good practices and opportunities at the European and national level	Internal & external	10
D.1.3 Reports from mobilisation and mutual learning workshops in the pilot areas	Internal	18
D.2.3 Lessons learned and policy recommendations from circular economy pilots	Internal & external	32
D.3.1 Local programmes for fostering circular economy	Internal & external	18
D.3.2 PDAs implementation models, operational services, and financing schemes	Internal & external	21
D.3.3 Potential risks and legal aspects of Programmes and PDAs	Internal & external	21
D.3.4 Sustainability and comparative analysis of pilots' experiences	Internal & external	36
D.4.2 Launch strategies from the pilots	Internal & external	22

D.5.7 Roadmap for DECISO scale-up	External	36
D.5.8 First CCRI-CSO policy brief	External	18
D.5.9 Second CCRI-CSO Policy Brief	External	36

5.2. DECISO's stakeholders

From a general perspective, DECISO's stakeholders would benefit from exploitation actions in a broad view, such as:

- **other regions/municipalities (LRA)**
 - All results can be used as a roadmap for the promotion of circular economy in their territories.
 - Guidelines for CEE Strategy; implement in their region/municipality.
 - Processes, business models, PDA, stakeholders' engagement: develop similar projects / pilots.
 - They can benefit from the experience and best practices shared by the DECISO project, particularly in terms of implementing circular economy projects, developing funding mechanisms, and establishing stakeholder networks. This knowledge can inform their own initiatives and help them navigate the complexities of project development and resource mobilization.
- **Public utility company (PU)**
 - Public utility companies can leverage the results of DECISO to enhance their understanding of rainwater management, circular economy principles, and sustainable resource utilization. This can assist them in developing innovative solutions for water management, optimizing infrastructure investments, and improving service delivery to customers.
 - Transfer of CE policy framework in their portfolio.
- **Financial actors (F)**
 - Implementing CE as an element in their financial funding portfolio
 - Agri-food circular economy funding schemes report – For the understanding of possible circular economy investments in the Agri food sector.
 - Financial actors, such as banks, investment firms, and funding agencies, can use the results of DECISO to assess the viability and potential impact of circular economy projects related to rainwater management. By gaining insights into successful project models, financial actors can make informed decisions about allocating resources and providing financial support to initiatives that align with sustainability objectives.
- **Enterprise / consulting (E)**
 - Implementing CE business models with the support of the CE network.
 - DECISO results - To enhance their business plans, to apply for new funding opportunities and to adopt the project best practices in order to become more circular.
 - Enterprises and consulting firms can benefit from the DECISO results by gaining access to valuable insights and expertise on circular economy practices, project development, and stakeholder

engagement. This knowledge can enable them to offer specialized services, develop innovative solutions, and support clients in implementing sustainable projects related to rainwater management.

- **Policymakers (P)**

- Anchoring CE/funding for CE business models in their policy frameworks: a) Business plan related to circular economy in the Agri-food sector (proposal); b) PDA documents; c) Alentejo region Circular economy in the Agri-food sector projects portfolio.
- Policymakers can make use of these results in order to influence circular economy public policies in the agri-food sector or others, and to promote new governance models related to Project Development Assistance. On the other hand, it will benefit them having the knowledge regarding the state of the art on the circular economy ecosystem in the region.
- Policymakers at local, regional, and national levels can utilize the results of DECISO to inform policy development, strategic planning, and decision-making processes related to circular economy initiatives and water management. By understanding best practices, policymakers can design effective regulatory frameworks, incentives, and funding mechanisms to promote sustainable development and address environmental challenges.

- **Research / Academia (R)**

- Gain knowledge about financing opportunities for transferring their research results into business ideas/models.
- Business plan related to circular economy in the Agri-food sector (proposal) – In order to use these results for future research.
- The research and academia community can leverage the findings and methodologies of DECISO to advance knowledge and understanding in the fields of circular economy, rainwater management, and sustainable resource utilization. This can contribute to the development of new theories, methods, and technologies to address pressing environmental issues and promote more resilient and sustainable communities.

- **Citizens / NGO (C)**

- Gain knowledge about CE through the CE network's PR activities; possibility to engage in activities.
- Alentejo region Circular economy in the Agri-food sector projects portfolio.
- Business plan related to circular economy in the Agri-food sector (proposal).
- Citizens may use this information to understand which agri-food products are more sustainable, which facilitates environmentally conscious purchasing decisions.
- Citizens and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) can benefit from the DECISO results by gaining awareness and understanding of circular economy concepts, rainwater management practices, and community engagement strategies. This can empower them to advocate for sustainable policies, participate in local initiatives, and contribute to collective efforts aimed at protecting the environment and enhancing quality of life.

5.2.1. Mapped stakeholders

DECISO deployed two main channels for stakeholders' mapping:

- 1) Direct engagement during the pilot local workshops (in task T1.3)
- 2) Online EU survey, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/ca55dfe0-43ac-f114-7efb-48bfaad5106f> thanks which we asked details for further engagement in project's activities. The survey is always on and running since (insert date)

The following table provides a list of stakeholders mapped during the project's scouting campaign that already have expressed their interest in joining DECISO's exploitation.

Table 7: Mapping of stakeholders and potential KERs to be deployed

Name	Kind	Co	Mapped by	Notes and potential benefits
ADC Moura	C	PT	Workshop	Solutions and practices
Amyndeon Wine (Amyndeon Oenos)	E	HE	Survey	Identify new business opportunities
ANFELMA S.r.l.	E	IT	Survey	Identify new business opportunities
Aromáticas d'Palma	E	PT	Workshop	Identify new business opportunities
Câmara Municipal de Borba	LRA	PT	Workshop	Portfolio of sustainable practices
Câmara Municipal de Mértola	LRA	PT	Workshop	Portfolio of sustainable practices
CICS-UBI	R	PT	Workshop	sharing Knowledge
DalenGuadiana	E	PT	Workshop	Identify new business opportunities
DETEPA - Municipal District Heating Company of Amindeo	PU	HE	Workshop	Portfolio of sustainable practices, processes, business models with high applicability potential,
DIADYMA	PU	HE	Workshop	Portfolio of sustainable practices, processes, business models with high applicability potential, PDA scaling up
ELEKTOR	E	HE	Workshop	Financial instruments: scaling up
Energy Competence Center	E	HE	Survey	sharing Knowledge, contribute to the scientific progresses for unsolved issues
Ervitas Catitas	E	PT	Workshop	Solutions and practices
EUROKOM	C	IT	Survey	Solutions and practices
INNORA, EKI	R	HE	Workshop	Sustainable practices and processes: Adapting sustainable practices and

				procedures for applicability across various industries
Innovative Research Applications PC	E	HE	Survey	Solutions and practices
Just Transition Institute Greece	C	HE	Workshop	Sustainable practices: raise awareness
MUNICIPAL WATER SUPPLY & SEWERAGE COMPANY OF KOZANI (DEYAK)	PU	HE	Survey	Portfolio of sustainable practices
Technical Chamber of Greece, Directorate of Forests (Regional Unity of Kozani)	P	HE	Workshop	Portfolio of sustainable practices: for bridging the legislative gap
Turismo de Portugal IP	P	PT	Workshop	Financial instruments, best practices
UBI-NECE	R	PT	Workshop	sharing Knowledge, contribute to the scientific progresses for unsolved issues
Universidade de Évora/MED	R	PT	Workshop	sharing Knowledge, contribute to the scientific progresses for unsolved issues
Caixa Agricola (bank)	F	PT	Pre-Existing contacts	Identify new business opportunities, booster CE and further developing of existing funding schemes and developing of new ones.
Circularity Capital https://circularitycapital.com/italy-home	F	IT	Desk Research	Focused strategy of investing in growth-stage companies in Europe's circular economy different sectors
CoreAngels https://www.coreangels.com/angel-groups/lisbon	F	PT	Desk Research	It's a global community of angel investors based in Portugal. Interested in scaling business in different sectors
FCH Finance City Hamburg (Public Private Partnership)	F	D E	pre-Existing contacts	Could be interested in various sectors, mostly in innovations
GLS Bank	F	D E	Desk research + pre-Existing contacts	Investing in different sectors
Hamburg Investors Network	F	D E	pre-Existing contact via working group	Could be interested in various sectors, mostly investing in innovative start-ups
Helektor SA	F	H E	Pre-Existing contacts	Financial instruments: scaling up, waste management sector
IFB Hamburg (Hamburg Innovation and Funding Bank)	F	D E	pre-Existing contacts	Offer funding for CE in SMEs (via PROFU Umwelt programme)
Innovation starter GmbH (LLC)	F	D E	pre-Existing contacts (member of working group)	Founding programme InnolImpact, funding social and environmental innovation
Planet Positive https://angel.co/planetpositive/syndicate	F	NL	Desk Research	angel investment syndicate based in the Netherlands, focus on invest in pre-seed and seed-stage climate tech companies

Raize https://www.raize.pt/	F	PT	Desk Research	No specific sector. Works on capital and investment loans
TEAL Impact https://tealimpact.vc/	F	PT	Desk research	angel investment syndicate based in Portugal. Focus on sustainability and environmental impact
The Gravity Incubator https://www.gravity.ventures/	F	CY	Desk research	angel investment syndicate based in Cyprus, also focus on bio-products using industrial by-product and waste streams.
The Green Angel Syndicate https://greenangelsyndicate.com/	F	UK	Desk research	angel investment syndicate based in United Kingdom. Focus on technologies for the B2C circular economy sector
Vienna Planet Fund https://vienna.business/planetfund/	F	AT	Desk Research	support city's climate strategy and help preserve planet for future generation

5.3. Critical analysis of exploitable KERs

A SWOT analysis and a risk assessment exercise have been carried out. Despite the ground information is limited to the first round of stakeholders' needs and requirements, it is possible to outline a significant project's potential profile to be used in the second period (M19-M36).

5.3.1. SWOT analysis for DECISO's exploitation

• Strengths

- The possibility to establish well-functioning CE networks in piloting territories that could act as relevant hubs for the whole regions. Within such networks, a CE contact point/ a CE hub serves as the centre for information on CE business plans/financing possibilities which can be provided for interested public, startups, SMEs, industry as well as a workshop for testing pilots etc.
- The consolidation of tools and instruments like the workshops, interviews, and focus groups, supporting the consortium in highlighting gaps in the legislative and funding layers for CE.
- The possibility to successfully implement CE solutions coupled with the establishment of a more structured approach to project development and acquiring relevant funding, as did – for example – for the rainwater scenario.
- Alongside the implementation of various CE solutions, the pilots aim at establishing a more structured approach to PDAs, which includes identifying funding opportunities, formulating project proposals, and securing financial resources, enhancing coordination among stakeholders, and maximising the likelihood of project success. Such dual achievements would not only demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of CE practices into pilots, but also provide replicable models for future initiatives in the regions and other territories.

• Weaknesses

- Lack of scalability or adaptability. Currently, at this first check of DECISO's competitiveness, the results that are tailored to specific contexts or conditions may struggle to remain competitive since they have not still been proven to be scalable or adaptable to different settings or evolving needs.
- The project's results could potentially become outdated over time if not correctly selected among the KERs and within the business models' propositions. Despite there would still be the possibility

of adapting these results to suit emerging contexts, the innovative characteristics could underperform against new technologies or AI-empowered solutions, for example.

- The timeframe for some KERs could be too extended to check their efficacy and monitor the pathways for future appropriation by other regions and territories.

● **Opportunities**

- Almost all KERs are transferable and replicable in other countries, but the different pre-conditions and other aspects should be considered. The opportunity is made by the political environment and trends favouring circular solutions and should be willing to invest into CE / to support CE by implementing financing schemes. Among the KERs we can list: Portfolio of sustainable practices, processes, business models, financing schemes increased awareness on successful, concrete, replicable and customizable examples of innovative and sustainable financing schemes, processes and business models, well-functioning in operational environment and high replicability potential. "
- The general structure and process offered by the DECISO project can indeed be utilised by other types of organisations. As demonstrated in the DECISO project through its four pilot regions with diverse topics and local conditions, the overarching framework and approach can be adapted and reproduced in different settings. The structured methodology for project development, stakeholder engagement, and resource mobilization can be applied across various sectors and contexts.
- The implementation of regional CE hubs could be the starting point of a circular economy clusters thanks to the feasibility demonstration and effectiveness of CE management and governance practices, as well as showcasing broader environmental benefits. As first step, we start with the initiatives implemented in Hamburg’s pilot and anchored in the climate plan
- With some scaling exercises, KERs can also be adapted to other sectors. In line of principle, institutions could use the portfolio for financing schemes and inform startups and SMEs more precisely about funding possibilities for CE. Those results could be used by SMEs, industry sector, universities, research and development agencies and clusters, Waste Management Facilities, Waste to Energy Plants, Medical Waste Incineration Plants, Biogas plants, Agricultural co operations. In addition, guidelines for CEE Strategies could be used by other cluster organizations for stakeholder engagement in other sustainable ecosystems. The following table provides an overview of potential additional sectors to be addressed by DECISO’s exploitation, given the knowledge at this project stage.

Table 8: Mapping KERs to other potential sectors (KERs’ codes in section 3.1)

Category	KER	Tourism	Manufacturing	Mobility	Food & Biomass	Waste	Textiles
Documents & Reports	1	-	X	X	X	X	X
	2	X	X	X	X	X	X
	3	-	-	-	X	X	-
	4	-	-	-	X	X	-

	5	X	-	X	X	X	X
Procedures and Practices	1	X	X	X	X	X	X
	2	X	-	X	X	X	X
	3	X	-	X	X	X	X
	4	X	X	X	X	X	X
	5	-	-	-	X	X	-
	6	-	-	-	X	X	-
Actions and Initiatives	1	X	X	X	X	X	X
	2	-	-	-	X	X	-
	3	X	-	X	X	X	X
	4	-	-	-	X	X	-
	5	X	X	X	X	X	X
Networking	1	X	X	X	X	X	X
	2	-	-	-	X	X	-
	3	X	X	X	X	X	X
	4	X	X	X	X	X	X

• Threats

- Resistance to change from stakeholders that may resist using results if they perceive that the findings could lead to changes in their current practices, procedures, or responsibilities. Resistance to change within organisations or sectors can pose a significant barrier to the adoption of new approaches or practices, even if they are supported by evidence or best practices. Overcoming entrenched attitudes or practices may require targeted efforts to build buy-in, address concerns, and demonstrate the benefits of embracing the DECISO results.
- Some stakeholders, especially smaller organizations, or those with constrained budgets, may face challenges in accessing the necessary resources, expertise, or funding to implement the recommendations or initiatives suggested by the DECISO results.
- Lack of investment in Research & Development, economic downturns can lead to stagnation and prevent the development of new, competitive products or services.
- Most of the stakeholders are SMEs in different EU Countries and might have difficulties in understanding English; so, the language can be a barrier as well.
- Regulatory changes or shifts in policy priorities, and changes in market conditions, consumer preferences, or industry trends could render the results obsolete if they no longer align with updated regulations or emerging policy frameworks.

Figure: 26 SWOT analysis

5.3.2. Potential risks, barriers, and countermeasures in DECISO exploitation

The potential risks and barriers that could hamper the use of results by stakeholders include:

Table 9: Risks, barriers, and countermeasures

Risk / barrier	Countermeasures
Not having informed the stakeholders or having chosen the “wrong” or “not so relevant” stakeholders for the project would be barriers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An intensive last-minute information plan focused on straight engagement strategies. • Adaptation of engagement approaches.
Lack of Access to Information: Limited access to the results due to issues such as data privacy, confidentiality, or restricted availability can hinder stakeholder engagement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure engagement activities follow ethical principles and rules.
Inadequate Communication: Poor communication of results can be a significant barrier.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted communication of the results, tailor-made to the category of stakeholder for facilitating the uptake of the KERs.
Lack of awareness: If stakeholders are unaware of the existence or relevance of the DECISO results, they may overlook valuable insights and miss opportunities for collaboration or improvement in their own practices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A tailor-made communication activity must be directed to each single category of stakeholders for explicitly explaining and showing the advantages of adoption of the DECISO result/s.

<p>Regulatory Changes: Changes in regulations and compliance requirements can affect the competitiveness.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each KER must include a procedure of constant review and update to new contexts and situations.
<p>Growing concerns by civil society and stakeholders about environmental impact and sustainability could limit the visibility and interest of DECISO's results .</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The presentation of the KER must always highlight its environmental impact and sustainability.
<p>The project's results could be considered obsolete or not optimising territorial needs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A scientific and constant review is recording any new finding of the scientific community, for being always aware of the progress in the concerned field.
<p>The obsolescence of results due to rapid technological advancements: If the results are based on technologies or methodologies that quickly become outdated or superseded by newer innovations, they may lose their competitiveness over time.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each KER must include a procedure of constant review and update to new contexts and situations.
<p>Legislative voids.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through stakeholders' engagement (mainly DECISO' workshops) it'd be possible to leverage the resources of both national and European public authorities to bring about regulatory adjustments, garner political backing, such as the establishment of programs, and tap into potential funding sources.
<p>Lack of motivated stakeholders and an interested civil society.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot partners should gather relevant (past and ongoing) projects, initiatives and partnerships in the regions and build on these experiences for creating a regional CE network.
<p>Challenges in replicating regional and territorial pilots. Specific pilots' structure and network established within each region are closely tied to local conditions and need a thorough consideration of the unique socio-economic, environmental, and institutional factors at play to be scaled.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While the lessons learned and best practices from the DECISO project can inform and inspire similar initiatives elsewhere, the exact replication of the pilot structure require balanced customisation to suit specific circumstances and objectives.

5.4. Potential actions for improving KERs in DECISO

The final exploitable KERs will be defined and refined during the second project phase; however, we can already argue about potential enhancements to be evaluated in thorough the pilots' progresses.

The exercise of improving KERs in and for the circular economy market usually involve enhancing the critical pivotal elements that drive sustainability, resource efficiency, and economic viability. In DECISO, the target at hand is to ensure both efficacy and usability of KERs, and their appeal to potential adopters or economic sponsor at large for replication of our portfolio of solutions in different scales. Therefore, the mentioned elements and parameters shall include the ones gathered from the OECD Inventory² and also used in the sustainability analysis performed in WP3, and the ones that will be elicited through interviews with private investors (category F in our stakeholders' classification). This means to validate reliable measurement procedures of each proposed improvements, followed by an evaluation of business capabilities and overall sustainability in the short to medium term. For DECISO the measurement layer is two-fold: a) within the pilots it is mandatory to optimise the environmental impact, so we will preliminarily focus on optimising processes and governance, minimising waste generation, increasing the reuse and recycling of materials, or maximising the value extracted from resources throughout their lifecycle, increasing the stakeholders' engagement and citizens' awareness. These are all common systemic elements which performances can be also compared among pilots; b) at the project level, KERs are the methods, procedures, and recommendations in defining and implementing the PDAs; they will be primarily monitored in their governance and social dimensions.

All these elements (*this is not an exhaustive list, indeed*) are expected to improve innovative business models that promote CEE and aim to achieve greater environmental benefits, reduce resource consumption, and enhance their competitive position within a rapidly evolving and increasingly sustainable market landscape and – consequently – answer to EC's policies main requests.

Once "measured", KERs will be improved by the means of different actions that we have classified into four macro-areas:

- **Stakeholders' balancing analysis**
 - Evaluate the role of each stakeholder in the definition of business or deployment models, and perform an exercise of tuning of KERs towards different scenarios embodying different roles and responsibilities among engaged stakeholders. The goal will be to provide evidence of KERs flexibility for further scalability options also based on different socio-economic boundaries.
- **Networking and engagement initiatives**
 - Empower stakeholders by involving them in the decision-making process. Facilitating the use of results for stakeholders involves proactive engagement and tailored communication strategies. To engage them, it's crucial to provide accessible and actionable information.
 - A targeted campaign is useful for the involvement of the public and the publication of the results of the project

² OECD Inventory of Circular Economy Indicators - ANDER, E. (2021). 1-The OECD Inventory of Circular Economy indicators

- The strong CE network engaging the different stakeholders and the cross-linking to other CE projects/actors/stakeholders is crucial for gaining publicity and give the interested persons access to the knowledge established in DECISO.
- Interactive Workshops and Meetings: Encourage open and constructive dialogue during workshops. Workshops for the relevant stakeholders for sharing the results of the project are important on a regular basis.
- Engage Early and Continuously: Provide updates and progress reports along the way to keep stakeholders informed and involved.
- Create a Feedback Loop: Establish a mechanism for stakeholders to provide input and feedback on how the results are being used and whether adjustments are needed.
- Segment stakeholders based on their level of interest and influence in the project or issue.
- Targeted outreach efforts, such as organizing workshops, webinars, and networking events to share insights, exchange best practices, and foster collaboration. To improve the impact of potential results, the project must ensure that the stakeholders engaged are people who do not just have high interest, but also have high influence over policy processes. As to the framework itself, the partnership should clarify to potential adopters whether it is meant for experienced professionals or foresight newbies; how much time and effort would be required to implement it in a new context; and perhaps provide a “lean” version of the strategies via online tools to those on low budgets and/or those who may be experiencing other resource constraints.
- **Communication activities**
 - To facilitate the use of results by the stakeholders, it's crucial to clearly communicate the findings and to tailor the reports to their specific needs. Also translate the main results and reports to native languages could facilitate the use of the results.
 - Continuous information of the public about the progress and news in the project is of great importance.
 - Clear Communication: Present the results in a clear and understandable manner, use visual aids, such as charts, graphs, and infographics, to illustrate key points and trends.
 - Customize Messages: Tailor messages to each stakeholder group's specific interests and concerns.
 - Building partnerships and networks, both within and across sectors, can also facilitate knowledge sharing and capacity building, enabling stakeholders to leverage the DECISO results to address specific challenges and opportunities in their respective domains.
 - Interactive presentations and feedback mechanisms encourage the engagement, while actionable recommendations provide direction for the decision-making process.
 - Transparency and engagement throughout the process build a trustful relation and a belonging feeling, while follow-up support ensures the effective implementation.
- **Documents and Tools**
 - Documentation: Ensure that results and discussions are documented and easily accessible to stakeholders who may need to refer back to them.

- Highlight Actionable Insights: Identify specific actions or decisions that can be taken based on the results. Make it clear how the information can be used to drive change or make improvements.
- User-friendly tools, guidelines, and resources can help stakeholders navigate complex issues and implement solutions more effectively.
- Leverage Technology: use of DECISO Digital Environment.

5.5. Considerations about the exploitation activities and update of the exploitation plan

As first observation, it becomes clear that the whole DECISO's paradigm brings to a broader view of exploitability of sustainable CEE practices in the territories, and, moreover, that the PDAs potential to ensure innovation is reliable for stakeholders. On the other hand, the acquisition processes of many practical solutions could need a considerable amount of bureaucratic work by local administrators and territorial agencies, leading to a potential delay in appreciating the whole potential for some KERs.

While considering all the countermeasures listed in Table 8, the second part of the project will be mainly devoted at two main exploitation goals:

- **Refine the KER's list** by:
 - selecting the most relevant and sustainable KERs and their adaptability to other stakeholders' and other territories' needs.
 - Defining a template for complete KERs description (only for most promising ones).
 - Adding KERs still to be identified during the project life.
- **Maximise the stakeholders' engagement** by:
 - Promoting the use of DECISO results obtained in the piloting areas:
 - Best practices and research on the market state of the art.
 - Novel models for analysing local programs; PDA implementation models; Model for cross-sectoral benchmarking; New or innovative way to deploy technical solutions for resource treatment.
 - Business models and financing schemes.
 - Leveraging upscaling actions:
 - Organise two workshops in Brussels aiming to create an interaction and discussion respectively with sister projects, and international and local stakeholders from different regions.
 - Workshops aiming also to build consensus about the project results.
 - Defining collaboration protocols with other networks
 - Sign at least 4 Memoranda of Understanding with other local or regional authorities or public utility companies.
 - 1 Workshop in Brussels to assess potentialities, sustainability and replicability and EU level to facilitate scale-up.

In addition, further tasks and related KPIs will be developed downstream of the project steering committees and will feed into updated versions of the project exploitation plan.

6. Annex 1

Table 10: Reach of DECISO communication activities

Activity	Date	Reach
National participatory workshop Hamburg	26/06/2023	32
National participatory workshop Alentejo		35
National participatory workshop Western Macedonia	03/07/2023	15
National participatory workshop Northwest Germany	26/04/2023	
Mutual Learning workshop Hamburg	06/09/2023	50
Mutual Learning workshop Alentejo	28/06/2023	20
Mutual Learning workshop Western Macedonia	30/11/2023	12
Mutual Learning workshop Northwest Germany	Aug-23	40
Financing local circular economy initiatives-HOOP/DECISO workshop	10/05/2023	2887
2 nd Forum CE Hamburg “Circular Cities”	12/04/2023	50
Kick-off meeting of the KARMA project	24/05/2023	50
Circular Economy Hotspot	29/05 – 01/06/2023	100
ACR+ General Assembly	31/05 – 01/06/2023	55
Circular Cities and Regions Conference	08/11/2023	100
ECOMONDO 2023		30
Financing and funding of circular business models and innovation	24/11/2023	1300
Cost efficiency in circular construction	28/11/2023	25
Pop-up Circular Hub	20/11 – 07/12/2023	1200
Open Day in JUPITER	13/04/2024	100000
WCEF2024 Side-Event: Hamburg and Opening of Pop-Up Circular Hub	30/04/2024	
ACR+ Newslines	08/04/2024; 22/04/2024; 13/11/2023; 23/10/2023; 15/05/2023	455
ACR+ Update	12/04/2023	1215
	TOTAL	107671

Table 11: Reach of social media posts

Partner	Date	Link or topic	Social media	Impressions
DECISO	04/03/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7181303339236683777	LinkedIn	363
DECISO	03/27/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7178790437141291009	LinkedIn	231
DECISO	02/15/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7165449984467832833	LinkedIn	209
DECISO	02/15/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7163826735480795136	LinkedIn	162
DECISO	02/06/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7160577604142477314	LinkedIn	144
DECISO	01/26/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7159108337018580992	LinkedIn	371
DECISO	01/26/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7158391136863072257	LinkedIn	241
DECISO	01/25/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7156579032350760961	LinkedIn	171
DECISO	01/24/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7155931104770695169	LinkedIn	266
DECISO	12/20/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7143162706810859520	LinkedIn	203
DECISO	12/06/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7138204350132269056	LinkedIn	129
DECISO	11/30/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7135918178731241472	LinkedIn	78
DECISO	11/22/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7133137582623735808	LinkedIn	103
DECISO	11/08/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7128015106889629696	LinkedIn	175
DECISO	11/08/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7127980127849766914	LinkedIn	61
DECISO	11/07/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7127612416586133504	LinkedIn	226

DECISO	11/02/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7125852891378032640	LinkedIn	211
DECISO	10/23/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7122224057814515712	LinkedIn	139
DECISO	10/19/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7120746644584738816	LinkedIn	458
DECISO	06/07/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072121595124686848	LinkedIn	87
DECISO	05/19/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7065346431615684610	LinkedIn	308
DECISO	05/10/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7061969715614601216	LinkedIn	174
DECISO	05/05/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7060267478538448896	LinkedIn	111
DECISO	19/05/2023 17:32	https://twitter.com/DECISOpject/status/1659582691061145602	X	250
DECISO	10/05/2023 09:54	https://twitter.com/DECISOpject/status/1656206139376168960	X	300
DECISO	08/05/2023 21:52	https://twitter.com/DECISOpject/status/1655661952549412864	X	2880
DECISO	25/10/2023 13:08	https://twitter.com/DECISOpject/status/1717135979738186080	X	40
DECISO	24/10/2023 14:08	https://twitter.com/DECISOpject/status/1716788796769841423	X	50
DECISO	23/10/2023 16:17	https://twitter.com/DECISOpject/status/1716458824188445038	X	40
DECISO	19/10/2023 14:54	https://twitter.com/DECISOpject/status/1714988270025588963	X	90
DECISO	30/11/2023 10:28	https://twitter.com/DECISOpject/status/1730156853953278400	X	100
DECISO	22/11/2023 18:03	https://twitter.com/DECISOpject/status/1727372251450974427	X	110
DECISO	08/11/2023 14:58	https://twitter.com/DECISOpject/status/1722252284820881632	X	90
DECISO	07/11/2023 12:18	https://twitter.com/DECISOpject/status/1721849706643341356	X	480

DECISO	02/11/20 23 15:38	https://twitter.com/DECISOPROJECT/status/1720087876225098060	X	30
DECISO	20/12/20 23 10:06	https://twitter.com/DECISOPROJECT/status/1737399080995733542	X	190
DECISO	06/12/20 23 17:39	https://twitter.com/DECISOPROJECT/status/1732439700411990106	X	530
DECISO	30/01/20 24 10:10	https://twitter.com/DECISOPROJECT/status/1752257844798271829	X	20
DECISO	26/01/20 24 10:42	https://twitter.com/DECISOPROJECT/status/1750816346424979479	X	10
DECISO	13/02/20 24 15:15	https://twitter.com/DECISOPROJECT/status/1757408030746882559	X	240
DECISO	08/02/20 24 11:15	https://twitter.com/DECISOPROJECT/status/1755535693919736095	X	40
DECISO	06/02/20 24 11:29	https://twitter.com/DECISOPROJECT/status/1754814686866895131	X	10
DECISO	02/02/20 24 10:33	https://twitter.com/DECISOPROJECT/status/1753350796589338635	X	0
DECISO	27/03/20 24 17:39	https://twitter.com/DECISOPROJECT/status/1773026946890252488	X	70
DECISO	05/19/20 23 08:05	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid02WJsJWXKxSfy3bNjWsfEdDRcG7eC8QRfEDvvd1TA1xYucR37FSzSQWogT6AYYpRCl	Faceboo k	211
DECISO	05/05/20 23 08:05	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid0QaykCbwwigt4F94q7SLrKiNwha8aNwFRPRMyn46MBmBds81HdFy1qqkgYVhpc1NJI	Faceboo k	153
DECISO	10/19/20 23 05:10	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid0j9npeudkSkj5Nu7jZLjnvdrhCDm8QLgmSCudSd1vEJmKoqJhgKDLYE1LC1BQaV8HI	Faceboo k	80
DECISO	10/23/20 23 07:10	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid02dEYSTwF2zGmpSGbg3nWZiYneYthT5zR3A6B5puUxaRwpNEp6X9xf6Q6oVGafT4Cil	Faceboo k	15
DECISO	10/23/20 23 11:10	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid0J4g8AZYcr9KUQf4eavkRKi2mZEoe6Tx7z2ETdxiz1PSw7mxqHkp6V5PYh1fDLJ41I	Faceboo k	15
DECISO	10/24/20 23 05:10	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid02Q2m8Eq3MG2dzmC5xWsUqoqgyJhXBKUQUSNZF1y8YtP6s3tFMBnZC5AjCWLukjyjEI	Faceboo k	23

DECISO	10/25/2023 04:10	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid02R3qyLUMRWJkNF5HrbAm1LVUz3Sx1DBAsAwC4rGggTRnt3QDZDxhkTUJHC1V2ERBWI	Facebook	81
DECISO	11/02/2023 07:11	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid02X89yq3VGb9ss5Wf83fDEHwVaWSskUPMR9HGgrEM2SkeUtnMNPedjX71HpyiAztWrl	Facebook	19
DECISO	11/07/2023 03:11	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid023YSpWN8Xq6b1CASEURGv1a4BnuNx6R6mcFbzLMLitza1GyExyGtRytgbowTGw8Uyl	Facebook	49
DECISO	11/08/2023 03:11	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid02taiPht628RBSdEoZ4yaBFqseP7q8cHmTrXVVGq9o8eFUtNcsQL74JsNreBdo93prl	Facebook	19
DECISO	11/08/2023 05:11	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid0KC6JTxdcwct52SGnYMB3W8BkNYeHEZUPaZ8jsv6dtUFh8YRE7jdNXjXKknCHyM1l	Facebook	29
DECISO	11/22/2023 09:11	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid02kWXjd3YCD1qsdgqc2oeiHoQQ3PR5jKkXju3GHsTBd8zdTo6jCo4ZmD9tTZQ5pfREl	Facebook	66
DECISO	11/30/2023 01:11	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid0rTJpc68rVzrnD9cckveDmdJ1A7ucwCFfZSUbAff7Wd7FQiKoVYZedwTNDqyQhpoql	Facebook	15
DECISO	12/06/2023 08:12	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid021cqHHEns35X3jFQS5hpn1ihf6vyyTzdREjBCjvtqx9QdJ695Rt3xmrwPvnjrTp5yl	Facebook	141
DECISO	12/19/2023 06:12	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid0KAtdFjL6jG9ooW1JFnZL7YMGLZMiFHwcQXRStEzezeFBfrxzPDkroLXznji2izYrl	Facebook	14
DECISO	12/20/2023 01:12	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid0gNpEQB9x2ZarZan7uhMvfceAhX1ndT4ixU5T8zpYkdE26m9Kv7oRzxJvoNzQyzLYl	Facebook	292
DECISO	01/25/2024 06:01	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid035CfBHh9pHpXxq7mEviBqYzjk1FBYPgX5DCRknvL4A5QjgNEZCQHyeCbfhL9aJM6ol	Facebook	18
DECISO	01/26/2024 04:01	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid06yY6q3uqgSgUMKVG8CBRWEQUhP3pngjGE8Xzhf31CbKp57hw1znewFQ4qvkgGM3RI	Facebook	17
DECISO	01/31/2024 01:01	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid03BUiUg7y1wkWcHx7NgSJ2V6RAtpzTGZzNx4XQGHo3Qt23KukkEwqwezvcjWtyAg7l	Facebook	45

DECISO	02/01/20 24 23:02	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid032QGF4KrwonYinPQ2bMMdnWbGc6QSbJWsoxuWCaQxvFnpsw1NJaK5nT8n5fi3Bq3UI	Facebook	51
DECISO	02/06/20 24 02:02	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid0igAJEsKsQcTH91egN9Bd4jh5tSPzjw9JtEmrKhh8ZxpByytUfQRNiN5aKLiCKMWrI	Facebook	20
DECISO	02/15/20 24 01:02	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid027DdBBB1hrD2xbUa9FM5aHKYrE3x9cQceWEg2en4BKgJSsze1XMuTYbr8EzcYUzDbI	Facebook	49
DECISO	02/19/20 24 01:02	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid02gGv8G1VxTtNTV8ie1pqWHReJZXNByuGrA6c2R8p4kL4jsS2UP3HDDZiggZ4kMAPvI	Facebook	181
DECISO	03/27/20 24 09:03	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid023jauZ37YXHPuoUgynAo1Qj3DfEos7dvbjF2Yn6dg3D6WSkjVdY3UNz4oZ2xw27Bkl	Facebook	59
DECISO	04/03/20 24 07:04	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid0i7qNvsvacPP7ni3eULgnomkWMenF5vCiYcNpzTjqtyjTbuJPBGDRaAx78ntvwQ3I	Facebook	34
DECISO	01/25/20 24 06:01	https://www.facebook.com/decisoproject/posts/pfbid035CfBHh9pHpXxq7mEvibYqZjk1FBYPgX5DCRknvL4A5QjgNEZCQHyeCbflL9aJM6ol	Facebook	18
CCDR	19/10/20 23	Announcement of conference	Facebook	126
	19/02/20 24	https://www.facebook.com/plugins/post.php?href=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.facebook.com%2Fccdralentejo%2Fposts%2Fpfbid02k2npxLCLZYhMKP4z1d9q9DWMYDLcF7qYrnHuJ7Vzk7z1MhDPtc8FJVZzv245R5Dil&show_text=true&width=500	Facebook	126
CCDR	23/10/20 23	DECISO ongoing conference	Facebook	126
Officinae Verdi	Feb-24	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7160214403001266176?updateEntityUrn=urn%3Ali%3Afs_feedUpdate%3A%28V2%2Curn%3Ali%3Aactivity%3A7160214403001266176%29	LinkedIn	272
University Western Macedonia (A. Krestou)	03/12/20 23	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7136963136162516992?updateEntityUrn=urn%3Ali%3Afs_feedUpdate%3A%28V2%2Curn%3Ali%3Aactivity%3A7136963136162516992%29	LinkedIn	14

EGEN	24/05/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/egen-grants-innovation-consultancy-horizoneurope-h2020-circulareconomy-activity-7067107679982247938-mghq?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	LinkedIn	270
University Western Macedonia (A. Krestou)	03/12/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/athina-athens-krestou-6b0884253_decisoabreu-activity-7136963986540965888-Ywh4?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	LinkedIn	14
CNR (P. Grifoni)	10/11/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/patrizia-grifoni-4000ab7_ccriconference2023-decisoproject-circulareconomy-activity-7128767606387277824-WT5U?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	LinkedIn	32
KOYS (F. Niglia)	15/04/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/francesconiglia_wcef2024-activity-7185599491146727425-tlUI?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	LinkedIn	47
Hamburg (S. Herrmann)	15/04/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/activity-7185572095626514433-M3oq?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	LinkedIn	40
CNR (P. Grifoni)	11/11/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/patrizia-grifoni-4000ab7_ccrieurope-ccriconference2023-activity-7129218618369687552-OmyL?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	LinkedIn	32
HOOP	10/05/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/hoop-project-ccrieurope-financing-circulareconomy-activity-7061981415487234048-X26h?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	LinkedIn	171
KOYS (F. Niglia)	08/11/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/francesconiglia_ccrieurope-eucircularsystemicsolutions-ccriconference2023-activity-7127943933971640320-Qi6c?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	LinkedIn	47
Bruno Marabotto (ETRA)	11/05/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7062354218560462848?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	LinkedIn	310

KOYS (F. Niglia)	23/05/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/francesconiglia_decisoabreu-activity-7066727744448925696-1Lc5?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	LinkedIn	47
ACR+ (e.Friesch)	09/05/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/elena-fries-tersch-4121304b_excited-to-announce-that-deciso-project-and-activity-7061651425411354624-EkOd?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	LinkedIn	43
ACR+	09/11/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7128329923374501888	LinkedIn	609
ACR+	19/10/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7120771401820565504	LinkedIn	1140
ACR+	10/05/2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7061977434799120385	LinkedIn	331
ACR+	24/10/2023	https://twitter.com/ACRplus/status/1716790692981141936	X	590
ACR+	10/05/2023	https://twitter.com/ACRplus/status/1656208129581785090	X	1920
ACR+	23/01/2024	https://twitter.com/ACRplus/status/1749747827666800761	X	360
TOTAL VIEWS				18572

